

N-(Aryl)pyrrole-2-alimine complexes of ruthenium: Synthesis, characterization and catalytic transfer-hydrogenation

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Reaction of N-(4'-R-phenyl)pyrrole-2-aldimines (HL-R, where H represents the acidic N-H hydrogen and, R = OCH₃, CH₃, H and Cl) with [Ru(bpy)₂(EtOH)₂]²⁺, formed *in situ* via Ag⁺-assisted removal of the chlorides from [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] in ethanolic medium, affords a group of pinkish-brown complexes of type [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]⁺ isolated as nitrate salts. Structure of [Ru(bpy)₂(L-OCH₃)]NO₃ and [Ru(bpy)₂(L-CH₃)]NO₃ have been determined by X-ray crystallography. The aldimine-ligand (L-R) is coordinated to the metal center as a mono-anionic bidentate N,N-donor. All the complexes are diamagnetic, and show characteristic ¹H NMR signals and intense absorptions in the visible region. Cyclic voltammetry on the complexes shows two irreversible oxidations within 0.64 to 1.14 V vs SCE and two irreversible reductions within -1.00 to -1.58 V vs SCE. The [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]⁺ complexes are found to serve as efficient catalyst-precursor for the transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones.

Keywords: N-(Aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines, 2,2'-bipyridine, ruthenium(II) complexes, crystal structure, catalytic transfer-hydrogenation.

Introduction

The current interest in the coordination complexes of ruthenium is largely due to their catalytic and biological applications¹. Such properties are dependent primarily on the coordination environment around the metal center, and hence binding of ruthenium by ligands of selected types is of significant importance. Herein we have chosen a group of four N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines as the principal ligand, which are abbreviated in general as HL-R, where H depicts the acidic N-H proton and R the *para*-substituent in the pendent phenyl ring. The four different substituents (R = OCH₃, CH₃, H and Cl), with different electron-withdrawing properties, have been chosen to study their influence, if any, on the redox properties of the resulting complexes. The selected ligands are known to bind to metal ions, via loss of the N-H proton, as mono-anionic N,N-donors forming stable five-membered chelate ring (I)². It may be mentioned here that while coordination chemistry of the N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines with few transition and non-transition metal ions has received some attention², that with ruthenium appears to have remained

less explored³. For the present study, [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] was chosen as the source of ruthenium because of its demonstrated ability to undergo facile displacement of the two chlorides by chelating bidentate ligands⁴. Understandably, the primary goal of the undertaken study was to synthesize mixed-ligand complexes of type [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]⁺. Reaction of the selected aldimine ligands (HL-R) with [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] has indeed been found to afford a family of mixed-ligand complexes of ruthenium

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nium. The chemistry of all these complexes is reported here, with special reference to their formation, characterization, and catalytic application.

Experimental

Materials:

Ruthenium trichloride was purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, and 2,2'-bipyridine was procured from Aldrich. $[Ru(bpy)_2Cl_2]$ was prepared by following a reported procedure⁵. Pyrrole-2-aldehyde was purchased from Spectrochem, Kolkata, and the *para*-substituted anilines were purchased from S.D. Fine-Chem Limited, Mumbai. The *N*-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines were prepared by condensing pyrrole-2-aldehyde with *para*-substituted anilines in hot ethanol. Tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBHP), obtained from Aldrich, and AR grade acetonitrile, procured from Merck, India, were used for electrochemical work. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received.

Syntheses of complexes:

The $[Ru(bpy)_2(L-R)]NO_3$ complexes were prepared by following a general procedure. Specific details are given below for a particular complex.

$[Ru(bpy)_2(L-OCH_3)]NO_3$: $[Ru(bpy)_2Cl_2]$ (100 mg, 0.21 mmol) was dissolved in warm ethanol (50 mL) and $AgNO_3$ (70 mg, 0.42 mmol) was added to it. The solution was gently warmed for 10 min. The solution was then filtered to remove the deposited $AgCl$, and to the filtrate *N*-(4'-methoxyphenyl)pyrrole-2-alimine (41 mg, 0.21 mmol) was added, followed by triethylamine (21 mg, 0.21 mmol). The solution was then refluxed for 3 h, whereby a brown solution was obtained. The solvent was then evaporated and the solid mass, thus obtained, was subjected to purification by thin layer chromatography on a silica plate. With acetonitrile as the eluant, a pinkish-brown band separated, which was extracted with acetonitrile. Evaporation of the acetonitrile extract gave $[Ru(bpy)_2(L-OCH_3)]NO_3$ as a dark crystalline solid. Yield: 72%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{27}N_7O_4Ru$: C, 56.96; H, 4.00; N, 14.54. Found: C, 56.88; H, 4.02; N, 14.51%; 1H NMR⁶: 3.65 (OCH_3), 6.15 (1H, s), 6.25 (2H, d, *J* 9.0), 6.39 (2H, d, *J* 9.0), 6.94 (2H, d, *J* 8.2), 7.17–7.24 (2H)*, 7.36 (2H, t, *J* 6.0), 7.47 (2H, t, *J* 6.0), 7.55 (H, d, *J* 6.0), 7.71 (2H, t, *J* 6.0), 7.93 (2H, d, *J* 8.4), 8.54 (2H, d, *J* 7.0), 8.60 (2H, t, *J* 6.4), 8.79 (2H, d, *J* 8.4); IR: 1633, 1605, 1561, 1505, 1481, 1443, 1419, 1384,

1303, 1263, 1244, 1185, 1121, 1104, 1084, 1064, 1038, 1021, 892, 836, 800, 730, 686, 657, 643, 603, 579 and 560 cm^{-1} .

$[Ru(bpy)_2(L-CH_3)]NO_3$: Yield: 70%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{27}N_7O_3Ru$: C, 58.35; H, 4.10; N, 14.89. Found: C, 58.25; H, 4.13; N, 14.87%; 1H NMR: 2.14 (CH_3), 6.13 (1H, s), 6.26 (2H, d, *J* 9.1), 6.37 (2H, d, *J* 9.2), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 8.0), 7.15–7.25 (2H)*, 7.34 (2H, t, *J* 6.4), 7.48 (2H, t, *J* 6.2), 7.53 (H, d, *J* 6.1), 7.72 (2H, t, *J* 6.3), 7.91 (2H, d, *J* 8.0), 8.55 (2H, d, *J* 7.3), 8.61 (2H, t, *J* 6.3), 8.77 (2H, d, *J* 8.7); IR: 1631, 1606, 1560, 1506, 1479, 1444, 1417, 1383, 1302, 1261, 1243, 1182, 1123, 1087, 1062, 1037, 1020, 893, 834, 801, 731, 685, 653, 643, 602, 577 and 561 cm^{-1} .

$[Ru(bpy)_2(L-H)]NO_3$: Yield: 73%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{25}N_7O_3Ru$: C, 57.75; H, 3.88; N, 15.21. Found: C, 57.69; H, 3.85; N, 15.23%; 1H NMR: 6.16 (1H, s), 6.21 (2H, d, *J* 9.2), 6.39 (2H, d, *J* 9.0), 6.94 (2H, t, *J* 8.3), 7.12–7.28 (3H)*, 7.36 (2H, t, *J* 6.4), 7.47 (2H, t, *J* 6.1), 7.55 (H, d, *J* 6.0), 7.71 (2H, t, *J* 6.2), 7.93 (2H, d, *J* 8.1), 8.54 (2H, d, *J* 7.4), 8.60 (2H, t, *J* 6.2), 8.79 (2H, d, *J* 8.8); IR: 1632, 1608, 1558, 1504, 1477, 1446, 1419, 1381, 1302, 1262, 1241, 1182, 1122, 1089, 1061, 1036, 1021, 893, 835, 802, 733, 688, 650, 642, 603, 578 and 560 cm^{-1} .

$[Ru(bpy)_2(L-Cl)]NO_3$: Yield: 76%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{24}N_7O_3Cl_1Ru$: C, 54.82; H, 3.54; N, 14.44. Found: C, 54.91; H, 3.56; N, 14.41%; 1H NMR: 6.15 (1H, s), 6.23 (2H, d, *J* 9.0), 6.36 (2H, d, *J* 9.1), 6.93 (2H, d, *J* 8.3), 7.14–7.25 (2H)*, 7.35 (2H, t, *J* 6.3), 7.46 (2H, t, *J* 6.0), 7.53 (H, d, *J* 6.2), 7.73 (2H, t, *J* 6.2), 7.89 (2H, d, *J* 8.3), 8.56 (2H, d, *J* 7.5), 8.63 (2H, t, *J* 6.3), 8.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.7); IR: 1631, 1605, 1552, 1501, 1475, 1442, 1417, 1380, 1301, 1261, 1239, 1180, 1121, 1090, 1062, 1037, 1021, 892, 835, 801, 731, 710, 684, 651, 641, 601, 577 and 561 cm^{-1} .

Physical measurements:

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a Sherwood MK-1 balance. 1H NMR spectra recorded in $CDCl_3$ solution on a Bruker Avance DPX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-630 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical measurements were made using a CH Instruments model 600 A electrochemical analyzer. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary

electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in the cyclic voltammetry experiments. All electrochemical experiments were performed under a dinitrogen atmosphere, and the electrochemical data were collected at 298 K. GC-MS analyses were performed using a Perkin-Elmer CLARUS 680 instrument.

X-Ray crystallography:

Single crystals of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-CH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ were obtained by slow evaporation of solvent from solutions of the respective complex in acetonitrile. Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). X-Ray data reduction and, structure solution and refinement were done using SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs⁷. The structures were solved by the direct methods. The structure of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]^+$ refined fairly well, while that of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-CH}_3)]^+$ did not due to poor data quality. In both the structures the nitrate ion was found to be severely disordered.

General procedure for the catalytic transfer-hydrogenation reactions:

In a typical run, an oven-dried 10 ml round-bottomed flask was charged with the aldehyde/ketone (1 mmol), a known mol percent of the catalyst, and KOH (0.1 mmol) dissolved in 2-propanol (5 ml). The flask was placed in a preheated oil bath at the required temperature. After the specified time, the flask was removed from the oil bath and water (20 ml) was added, neutralized with 1(M) HCl, and extracted with diethyl ether (4–10 ml). The combined organic layers were washed with water (3–10 ml), dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and filtered. Diethyl ether was removed under vacuum and the residue obtained dissolved in hexane and analyzed by GC-MS.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization:

As outlined in the introduction, the initial goal of the present work was to synthesize a family of mixed-ligand ruthenium(II)

Table 1. Crystallographic data for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-CH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$

	$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$	$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-CH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{Ru}$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_7\text{O}_3\text{Ru}$
Formula weight	1349.35	1317.35
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Triclinic
Space group	Cc	$P\bar{1}$
<i>a</i> (Å)	18.5981(15)	13.6445(12)
<i>b</i> (Å)	19.9029(16)	13.6485(13)
<i>c</i> (Å)	17.3073(14)	17.0809(16)
α (°)	90	97.569(3)
β (°)	102.568(2)	97.562(2)
γ (°)	90	94.323(2)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	6252.9(9)	3111.8(5)
<i>Z</i>	4	2
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (mg/m ³)	1.433	1.406
<i>F</i> (000)	2752	1344
Crystal size (mm)	0.07×0.11×0.26	0.16×0.22×0.24
<i>T</i> (K)	296	296
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.549	0.548
Collected reflections	34878	22963
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.048	0.072
Independent reflections	12921	10455
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a	0.1007	0.2590
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.2745	0.4830
GOF ^c	0.85	3.40

^a $R_1 = \sum ||F_o| - |F_c|| / \sum |F_o|$. ^b $wR_2 = [\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum [w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}$. ^cGOF = $[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / (M - N)]^{1/2}$, where M is the number of reflections and N is the number of parameters refined.

complexes containing N-(4'-R-phenyl)pyrrole-2-alimine (HL-R) and 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy). Accordingly, reactions of the selected aldimine ligands were carried out with $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{EtOH})_2]^{2+}$, which was formed *in situ* via Ag^+ -assisted removal of the two chlorides from $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ in ethanolic medium. The targeted $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-R})]^+$ complexes, thus generated (Scheme 1), were isolated as their nitrate salts in good yields. Preliminary characterizations on these complexes were found to be consistent with their compositions. However, for an unambiguous identification of these complexes, structure of two selected members, viz. $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-CH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$, were

Scheme 1. Formation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-R})]^+$.

determined by X-ray crystallography. The structures are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, and some relevant bond parameters are listed in Table 2. Both the structures show that the aldimine ligand is coordinated to ruthenium in the expected mono-anionic bidentate chelating mode (I, M = Ru) with a bite angle of about 78°. Two bpy ligands are also coordinated to the metal center. Ruthenium is thus nested in a N₆ coordination environment, which is distorted octahedral in nature, as evident from the bond parameters around the metal center. In the Ru(L-R) (R = OCH₃, CH₃) fragment, the two Ru-N distances are quite normal, and so are the bond distances within the chelated aldimine ligand. The bond parameters within the Ru(bpy)₂ fragment are also found to be usual. As all four [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes were synthesized similarly, and they show similar properties (*vide infra*), the remaining two [Ru(bpy)₂(L-H)]⁺ and [Ru(bpy)₂(L-Cl)]⁺ complexes are assumed to have similar structures as [Ru(bpy)₂(L-OCH₃)]⁺ or [Ru(bpy)₂(L-CH₃)]⁺.

Spectral studies:

Magnetic susceptibility measurements show that the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes are diamagnetic, which is consistent with the +2 oxidation state of ruthenium (low-spin

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-OCH₃)]⁺ complex (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity).

Fig. 2. Crystal structure of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-CH₃)]⁺ complex (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity).

Table 2. Selected bond distances and bond angles

[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L-OCH ₃)]NO ₃			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru1-N1	2.123(12)	Ru1-N3	2.061(11)
Ru1-N2	2.083(13)	Ru1-N4	2.042(11)
C5-N2	1.29(2)	Ru1-N5	2.038(12)
		Ru1-N6	2.044(13)
Bond angles (°)			
N1-Ru1-N5	171.5(5)	N1-Ru1-N2	75.5(5)
N2-Ru1-N4	171.8(5)	N3-Ru1-N4	78.3(5)
N3-Ru1-N6	173.4(4)	N5-Ru1-N6	76.3(5)
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L-CH ₃)]NO ₃			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru1-N1	2.051(14)	Ru1-N3	2.084(17)
Ru1-N2	2.118(14)	Ru1-N4	2.054(14)
C5-N2	1.25(2)	Ru1-N5	2.091(17)
		Ru1-N6	2.096(15)
Bond angles (°)			
N1-Ru1-N5	173.5(6)	N1-Ru1-N2	77.9(5)
N2-Ru1-N4	170.7(6)	N3-Ru1-N4	78.7(7)
N3-Ru1-N6	174.8(7)	N5-Ru1-N6	78.4(7)

d⁶, S = 0) in them. ¹H NMR spectra of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes show many signals arising from the coordinated aldimine and bpy ligands, most of which could be easily identified, while few could not be clearly detected due to overlap problem. For example, signals for the methyl group in

[Ru(bpy)₂(L-OCH₃)]NO₃ and [Ru(bpy)₂(L-CH₃)]NO₃ are observed at 3.65 ppm and 2.14 ppm respectively. A clean singlet observed near 6.15 ppm is assigned to the azomethine proton. A doublet is observed in all the spectra at around 8.78 ppm as the most deshielded signal, which is assignable to an *ortho*-proton of a coordinated bpy ligand.

Infrared spectra of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes show many bands of different intensities in the 450–4000 cm⁻¹ region, and assignment of the bands to specific vibrations has not been attempted. However, comparison with spectra of the corresponding uncoordinated aldimine ligands shows that the N-H stretch, observed in the free aldimine ligands near 3211 cm⁻¹, is absent in the complexes, confirming deprotonation during complexation. A strong band near 1348 cm⁻¹ is observed in all the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes, indicating presence of the nitrate ion. Several sharp bands (near 1633, 1605, 1505, 1443, 1419, 1384, 1303, 1121, 1021, 836 and 730 cm⁻¹) are observed in the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes, which were absent in [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂], and hence these are attributed to the coordinated aldimine ligand. The ¹H NMR and infrared spectral data are therefore in good agreement with the composition of the complexes.

The [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes are found to be readily soluble in polar organic solvents, such as: dichloromethane, chloroform, acetonitrile, etc., producing intense pinkish-brown solutions. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in dichloromethane solutions. Spectral data are presented in Table 3. Each complex shows six absorptions spanning the visible and ultraviolet regions. The lowest energy absorption, displayed by all four complexes near 520 nm, is believed to be due to a metal-to-ligand charge-transfer transition. The intense absorptions in the ultraviolet region are attributable to transitions within the ligand orbitals.

Electrochemical properties:

Electrochemical properties of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes have been studied by cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP). Each complex shows two oxidative responses on the positive side of SCE and two reductive responses on the negative side. All the responses are found to be irreversible in nature. Cyclic voltammetric data are given in Table 3. The first oxidative response near 0.65 V vs SCE is assigned to Ru^{II}-Ru^{III} oxidation. In [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺, this oxidation occurs at 1.30 V vs SCE⁸. Therefore, replacement of only one bpy by an aldimine (L-R) ligand has caused a negative shift of about 650 mV. In spite of presence of the π-acidic imine fragment in the L-R ligand, this large shift in oxidation potential shows the ability of the anionic pyrrole-nitrogen to stabilize the trivalent state of ruthenium. The second oxidation is tentatively assigned to Ru^{III}-Ru^{IV} oxidation. The two reductive responses are attributable to reduction of the two coordinated bpy ligands. Potential of the redox responses in the [Ru(bpy)₂(L-R)]NO₃ complexes does not show any systematic variation with the nature of the substituent R in the aldimine ligands.

Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation:

Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones, with 2-propanol as the hydrogen provider, has been receiving considerable attention⁹, primarily because of the green nature of the methodology. Such reactions are known to be efficiently catalyzed by a variety of ruthenium(II) complexes¹⁰, where the reactions usually proceed through the intermediacy of a ruthenium-hydrido species. Hence, complexes having a pre-existing Ru-H bond, or with the potential of formation of a Ru-H bond *in situ*, are suitable for trial as transfer-hydrogenation catalyst. As complexes with a Ru-X (X = halide, pseudohalide, or other anionic ligand) bond are

Table 3. Electronic spectral and cyclic voltammetric data

Complex	Electronic spectral data ^a λ _{max} , nm (ε, M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Cyclic voltammetric data ^c E/V vs SCE
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L-OCH ₃)]NO ₃	521 (9800), 462 ^b (8200), 381 (15600), 335 (17300), 292 (55800), 247 (31400)	1.14 ^d , 0.66 ^d , -1.58 ^e , -1.05 ^e
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L-CH ₃)]NO ₃	521 (11600), 461 ^b (9200), 380 (18100), 332 (18700), 294 (56400), 246 (31200)	1.11 ^d , 0.65 ^d , -1.53 ^e , -1.03 ^e
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L-H)]NO ₃	520 (13300), 462 ^b (11000), 380 (20100), 331 (22700), 294 (69700), 247 (37900)	1.08 ^d , 0.64 ^d , -1.47 ^e , -1.00 ^e
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (L-Cl)]NO ₃	519 (12000), 460 ^b (10600), 382 (17600), 335 (23500), 295 (57300), 246 (33400)	1.09 ^d , 0.67 ^d , -1.51 ^e , -1.08 ^e

^aIn dichloromethane. ^bShoulder. ^cSolvent, acetonitrile; supporting electrolyte, TBHP; scan rate, 50 mV s⁻¹. ^dE_{pa} (anodic peak potential) value. ^eE_{pc} (cathodic peak potential) value.

Table-4 (contd.)

known to provide a Ru-H fragment upon reaction with primary or secondary alcohols¹¹, we wanted to explore such possibility in the present complexes where an anionic pyrrole-nitrogen is linked to ruthenium. We began our exploration by examining the transfer-hydrogenation of benzophenone to benzhydrol using $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ as the catalyst-precursor. After extensive optimization we found that 1.0 mol% catalyst, 0.1 mmol KOH, 2-propanol as solvent, a reaction temperature of 85°C, and a reaction time of 12 h furnished an excellent yield (89%) of the targeted product (Table 4, entry 1). As all the ruthenium complexes were found to show comparable catalytic efficiency, only the results obtained with $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ as the catalyst are presented here. Using the optimized reaction conditions, transfer-hydrogenation of ten different substrates, both aldehydes and ketones, have been performed (Table 4, entries 1–10).

Table 4. Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones^a

Entry	Substrate	Yield ^b (%)
1		89
2		83
3		87
4		70
5		88

6		90
7		66
8		76
9		77
10		55

^aReaction conditions: aldehyde or ketone (1.0 mmol), KOH (0.1 mmol), 2-propanol (5 ml), catalyst: $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$, reaction temperature (85°C), time (12 h). ^bDetermined by GC-MS.

The product alcohols were obtained in good to excellent yields for all the substrates (entries 1–9) except 2-formylpyridine, where the product alcohol was obtained in slightly less yield (entry 10). The fact, that the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-R})]\text{NO}_3$ complexes are found to efficiently catalyze transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones using 2-propanol as the hydrogen donor, testifies the *in situ* generation of a Ru-H fragment. The probable steps behind formation of such a hydrido species are illustrated in Scheme 2. In the initial step, 2-propanol cleaves the Ru-N_{pyrrole} bond, which had dominant ionic character, and thus generates a new species **A**. In the following step β -hydride elimination from the coordinated alkoxide takes place to produce acetone, and a new species **B** having a Ru-H bond. The *in situ* generated hydrido species (**B**) is believed to have served as the catalytically active species. Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation with Ru-complex having chelated anionic ligand as pre-catalyst is precedent in the literature^{11d}. The observed catalytic activity of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L-OCH}_3)]^+$ is comparable to that of some reported ruthenium(II) complexes¹².

Scheme 2. Generation of Ru-hydride species (positive charge on the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}-\text{R})]^+$ complex, and the two derived species **A** and **B**, is not shown).

Conclusion

The present study shows that the N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines (HL-R) can undergo facile reaction with $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ assisted by Ag^+ , and form mixed-ligand $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}-\text{R})]^+$ complexes. This study also demonstrates that the Ru-N_{pyrrole} bond can be successfully utilized for *in situ* generation of a Ru-hydrido species, which can be further utilized for catalytic transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}-\text{OCH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}-\text{CH}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC 1847020-1847021.

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